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Alley Cropping Can Potentially Alter the Nitrogen and Carbon Soil Cycles and Increase the Abundance of Beneficial Bacteria in a Mediterranean Citrus Orchard

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ABSTRACT

Monocrop of mandarin leading to reduced soil biodiversity and functionality that must be changed to a sustainable agriculture practice such as alley cropping. In this study an attempt has been made to assess how two different alley cropping strategies promote soil bacterial diversity, microbial activities and the abundance of beneficial bacteria. Three treatments were established: (i) mandarin monoculture (MC); (ii) mandarin diversified with barley/vetch (summer) and with fava bean (winter) for 3 consecutive years (DIV1); and (iii) mandarin diversified with fava bean, purslane and cowpea (DIV2). Results reveal that alley cropping did not significantly affect alpha-diversity indices, but beta-diversity showed significant differences among the three treatments, indicating changes in the bacterial community. Specific genera such as *Haliangium*, *Microbacterium*, *Pseudonocardia*, *Solirubrobacter* and *Sphingomonas*, known as plant growth-promoting bacteria, showed higher relative abundances in DIV1 and DIV2 than MC. The genus *Novosphingobium* showed a higher relative abundance in DIV2, while *MND1* showed a higher relative abundance in DIV1. Regarding potential gene abundances related to C and N cycling at the end of the experiment, only *manB* (hemicellulose degradation) showed a higher abundance in DIV2 than MC, while *nifH* (N fixation), *amoA*, and *hao* (nitrification) showed higher values in DIV1 and DIV2. Enzyme activities showed lower values in diversified treatments than in MC. Most significant changes were observed in the diversification of the alley with a sequence of different crops every year (DIV1), rather than repeating the same crops (DIV2). These alley cropping strategies (DIV1 and DIV2) seem an effective strategy to enhance the abundance of beneficial bacteria with increased potential activity related to N fixation and nitrification.

1 | Introduction

Citrus tree orchards are primarily based on monocultures, with bare ground and a large amount of external inputs (e.g.,

pesticides, fertilizers) affecting human health, ecosystem, and soil sustainability (Liu et al. 2017) functionality that must be changed to a sustainable agriculture practice with minimal agricultural inputs and healthy food (Bünemann et al. 2018)

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such as alley cropping. Considering that diseases as *Alternaria sp.*, *Colletotrichum sp.*, *Phytophthora sp.*, *Xanthomonas fragariae* (*X. fragariae*), *Botrytis cinerea* (*B. cinerea*), *Xylella fastidiosa* (*X. fastidiosa*), *Xanthomonas campestris pv. campestris* (*X. campestris pv. campestris*) impose significant production constraints affecting both yield and overall quality of crop (Lei et al. 2023; Caserta et al. 2014; Hao et al. 2019; Poveda et al. 2021).

Alley cropping is defined as the planting of rows of trees and/or shrubs to create alleys within which agricultural or horticultural crops are produced. Alley cropping could be a suitable strategy to increase land profitability by production of complementary commodities in the same space during the same year (Yang et al. 2021). Also, it has important roles in preserving biodiversity by providing complementary habitats and improved ecosystem services (Ashraf et al. 2018). If crops are properly selected and managed, alley crops can increase soil organic matter content in the soil due to the greater diversity and quantity of root litter contributing to soil C sequestration (Reyes et al. 2021). It can increase soil fertility providing a more suitable habitat for the rapid growth of microorganisms that can fix atmospheric N or solubilize soil nutrients (Beule and Karlovsky 2021) and can attract pollinators and auxiliary fauna to fight against pests (Morugán-Coronado et al. 2020). Also, increase soil biodiversity due to the tree rows strongly shape soil microbial communities and harbour a microbiome that is compositionally distinct from that of the neighbouring crops (Beule et al. 2022).

Legumes have a critical role in building the natural ecosystem, agriculture and agroforestry. The service rendered by legumes, other than a protein-rich diet to mankind, also maintains an ecological balance in terms of the N cycle via biological nitrogen fixation (BNF) through beneficial bacteria (e.g., *Rhizobium*), addition of N-rich biomass, and an increase of soil available phosphorus content. This enhances plant productivity, and it affects the activity and composition of the soil microbial community. What, in turn reduces the load of synthetic nitrogenous fertilizer and greenhouse gas emission (Mrunalini et al. 2022). Latati et al. (2013, 2014) highly recommended as alley crops in orchards.

Microorganisms contribute to soil functionality and the delivery of ecosystem services through their participation in biogeochemical cycles (e.g., C, N, P or S). They transform and increase soil available nutrients (Urbanová et al. 2015) and through active interactions of pathogen microorganisms and suppressive microbes inhibit soil-borne diseases (Niu et al. 2020). Alley cropping systems have a substantial impact on the composition of microbial communities (Cuartero et al. 2022) due to the effect of roots of different plant species on soil microbial diversity, structure, activity and functionality (Lian et al. 2019). Liu et al. (2024) observed that the quantity of soil microbiota of alley cropping was generally higher than monocropping and Granzow et al. (2017) observed that bacterial and fungal diversity in the rhizosphere soil of mixed-cropping (wheat/legume) was significantly higher than in soils from both monoculture scenarios.

Among the many microorganisms that live in the soil, it is possible to identify genera and species that are critical for maintaining soil fertility. They are called beneficial soil microorganisms, and their abundance in the soil is an indicator of soil

health. It seems that most interesting group is plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR), nitrogen-fixing and biocontrol microorganisms (Streletskaia et al. 2024). Most studied PGPR are the representatives of Pseudomonadota and Bacillota phyla, for example, strains of *Bacillus*, *Pseudomonas*, *Acinetobacter*, *Serratia*, *Burkholderia*, *Rhizobium* and *Azotobacter* genera (Ramakrishna et al. 2019). Nitrogen fixation of prokaryotes is observed both in free-living soil bacteria and in bacteria spatially associated with plants in the root zone or directly interacting with them, for example, strains of *Rhizobium*, *Frankia*, *Azotobacter*, *Azospirillum*, *Beijerinckia*, *Mycobacterium*, *Bacillus* or *Pseudomonas* genera (Soumare et al. 2020). Also, other microorganisms can be an integral part of plant nutrient management and pest and disease control practices.

Intercropping may thus affect the soil microbial community diversity and composition via changes in the contents of soil nutrients and enzyme activities. Furthermore, soil microorganisms do not occur independently but instead form complex ecological interaction webs to maintain ecosystem functions (Delgado-Baquerizo et al. 2016).

The aim of this work was to add evidences of the use of alley cropping mandarin trees/legumes on soil microbial community responsible of soil sustainability and functionality that has been scarce study. Assessing the best behaviour of legume patterns crops and mandarin tree alley cropping.

2 | Materials and Methods

2.1 | Study Site and Experimental Design

This study was carried out from February 2018 to February 2021 in a commercial citrus tree orchard (*Citrus reticulata* (*C. reticulata*) Blanco var. *Clemenvilla*), located in Murcia, SE Spain (37° 57' 31" N; 0° 56' 17" W) with a semi-arid Mediterranean climate. The soil properties were detailed in Sánchez-Navarro et al. (2023). The *C. reticulata* orchard was planted in 2000, it covered an area of 2.3 ha, with 970 trees planted, with a space of 6 m between rows and 4 m between trees within the same row. A drip irrigation system was installed along all the mandarin tree rows. The irrigation per tree was (4 L h⁻¹) ranging from 1 to 2 times per week in winter, 2 to 7 times per week in spring and autumn and 7 to 14 times per week in summer.

Three different treatments were established as split-plot designs with three replicates in September 2018. Plots measuring 12 m × 28 m were set up and including three rows of six trees. Treatments were: (i) mandarin monoculture (MC) with no alley cropping; (ii) mandarin diversified (DIV1) with barley/vetch (*Hordeum vulgare* L./*Vicia sativa* L.) grown from February to June 2018, 2019 and 2020 and with fava bean (*Vicia faba* (*V. faba*) L.) grown from September to December 2018, 2019 and 2020 as alley cropping; and (iii) mandarin diversified (DIV2) with fava bean (*V. faba* L.) grown from September 2018 to December 2019; purslane (*Portulaca oleracea* L.) grown from May to July 2019, and cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* (L.) Walp) grown from June 2020 to September 2020 as alley crops (Figure 1). The agricultural management was described in Sánchez-Navarro et al. (2023).

FIGURE 1 | Schedule of the crops grown in the different diversification strategies. The red marks indicate the approximate harvest dates of the mandarin trees 21/02/2019 and 17/02/2021. DIV1, mandarin diversified with barley/vetch and fava bean; DIV2, mandarin diversified with fava bean, purslane and cowpea; MC, monocrop with bare alley soil.

2.2 | Soil Sampling

Two soil sampling campaigns were performed on 21/02/2019 and 17/02/2021 at 0–10 cm with an auger. Three composite samples derived from five random subsamples were collected in each plot in the middle of the alley. Thus, we had 9 samples per treatment (3 composite samples \times 3 plots) (Özbolat et al. 2023). Soil cores using steel cylinders (5 cm high \times 5 cm diameter (98 cm³)) were taken to determine bulk density (BD). Soil samples were divided into two: one was kept at ambient temperature for physicochemical analyses, and the other was stored at 4°C for biological analyses.

2.3 | Soil Physicochemical Analyses

Soil water content at -1500 kPa (wilting point, SWW) and soil water content at -33 kPa (field capacity, SWFC) were measured using Soil Moisture Equipment (Corp., Santa Barbara, CA, USA). pH and electrical conductivity (EC) were measured in soil to water ratio (1:2.5 and 1:5 w/v), respectively. Inorganic carbon (IC) and total nitrogen (TN) were determined by an elemental CHNS-O analyzer (EA-1108, Carlo Erba). TOC was measured after removing soil carbonates by adding HCl in an elemental CHNS-O analyzer (EA-1108, Carlo Erba). Cation exchange capacity (CEC) and exchangeable Ca, Mg were determined according to ISO13536 (1995).

Particulate organic carbon (POC), bulk density (BD) and the content of sand, clay and silt were measured based on the methods recorded in the *Handbook of Plant and Soil Analysis for Agricultural Systems* (Alvaro-Fuentes et al. 2019).

2.4 | DNA Extraction and Sequencing

DNA extraction and sequencing were performed according to Cuartero et al. (2021). A brief description: DNA extraction from the soil was carried out with a DNeasy PowerSoil Pro Kit (QIAGEN), following the manufacturer's instructions using 0.5 g of soil. Bacterial (16S hypervariable regions) amplification was performed with Ion 16S Metagenomics Kit (ThermoFisher Scientific), the library was developed with Ion Xpress Plus gDNA Fragment Library Preparation Kit (ThermoFisher Scientific) combined with the Ion Xpress Barcode Adapters kit (ThermoFisher Scientific) and finally, sequencing was performed with Ion Sphere Particles (ISPs) via Ion OneTouch 2 System with suitable Ion PGM Hi-Q View OT2 Kit (ThermoFisher Scientific) followed by the enrichment of ISPs using Ion OneTouch ES. Sequencing reaction was carried out with the Ion PGM System, Ion PGM Torrent Server and the appropriate Ion PGM Hi-Q View Sequencing kit (ThermoFisher Scientific) in competence with sequencing chips from the Ion 316 Chip v2 kit.

2.5 | Enzyme Activities

The soil enzyme activities β -1,4-glucosidase (B-gluco), leucine aminopeptidase (LA), β -1,4-*N*-acetylglucosaminidase (GlcNac) and phosphatase (Phosphatase) were measured using the fluorogenic approach following Marx et al. (2001). The dehydrogenase activity (DH) in soil was measured using a colorimetric procedure following Von Mersi and Schinner (1991). The detailed protocol for measuring the enzyme activities is recorded in the *Handbook of Plant and Soil Analysis for Agricultural Systems* (Alvaro-Fuentes et al. 2019).

2.6 | Soil Borne Pathogens

The presence of different pathogens (*Alternaria sp.*, *Colletotrichum sp.*, *Phytophthora sp.*, *X. fragariae*, *B. cinerea*, *X. fastidiosus*, *X. campestris pv. campestris*) were estimated in the different samples. The quantification was carried out from the extracted soil DNA in a real-time quantitative PCR (qPCR) by using 7500 Fast Real-Time PCR system (Applied Biosystems, Foster City, California, USA) following the PCR protocol by Santísima-Trinidad et al. (2018).

2.7 | Bioinformatics

The initial raw reads of bacterial 16S rRNA were processed to remove barcodes and primers using the BaseCaller application. Then, the sequences were denoised through ACACIA (Bragg et al. 2012). After that, low-quality sequences were filtered out using the Quantitative Insights Into Microbial Ecology (QIIME) pipeline (Caporaso et al. 2010). Reads with low quality scores were removed, and the remaining sequences were filtered for chimeras using VSEARCH (Rognes et al. 2016), with the ribosomal database project (RDP database) as a reference. The valid reads were then grouped into Operational Taxonomic Units (OTUs) based on $\geq 97\%$ similarity with the SILVA reference database 128, as previously done in Cuartero et al. (2021, 2022). The potential genes were predicted from the OTU table using Phylogenetic Investigation of Communities by Reconstruction of Unobserved States (PICRUSt) (Langille et al. 2013).

2.8 | Statistical Analysis

For physicochemical properties, enzyme activities, and functional genes, normal distribution using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov were checked. Data were submitted to a one-way ANOVA to assess the differences among treatments (MC, DIV1, and DIV2), followed by Tukey's HSD test for the significant variables at $p < 0.05$.

The biodiversity indices Shannon diversity index (H') and Hill numbers were assigned by using R packages *iNEXT* v3.0.1 and *vegan* v2.6-4 (Oksanen et al. 2019). The differences among the different groups in terms of biodiversity indices were calculated by one-way ANOVA after testing the assumptions of normality and homoscedasticity. As a non-parametric alternative, we employed the Kruskal–Wallis test. The bacterial community structure was represented using Principal Coordinate Analysis (PCoA), and the statistical differences were tested using the Permutational Multivariate Analysis of Variance (PERMANOVA) with 999 permutations.

To assess the effect of the soil's physicochemical properties and bacterial community, Redundancy analysis (RDA) was performed using the bacterial community at the genus level as a response matrix and soil physicochemical parameters as an explanatory matrix for T3. Bacterial genus data were transformed by using the Hellinger transformation prior to applying the 'RDA' function of the *vegan* package. The *ggplot2* v3.3.5 was used to visualize the two-dimensional RDA1 \times RDA2 plot with

significant explanatory variables as vectors of physicochemical properties and data points as the bacterial population (Oksanen et al. 2019). (R Core Team 2023).

3 | Results

3.1 | Effects of Alley Cropping on Bacterial Diversity

The Shannon index and Hill's diversity index (at $Q = 0$, $Q = 1$ and $Q = 2$) showed no significant differences among the treatments on both sampling dates (Figures S1 and S2). However, there were significant differences in beta diversity ($p < 0.05$) among the treatments on both sampling dates and in all the pairwise comparisons (Figure 2). On the two sampling dates, DIV2 exhibited the most divergent structure compared to MC. In contrast, DIV1 showed a temporal evolution in its community structure. It clustered closer to MC in 2019 but became significantly more divergent in 2021.

3.2 | Effects of Alley Cropping on Bacterial Community Composition

Actinobacteriota and Pseudomonadota were the dominant bacterial phyla on both sampling dates (Figure 3A,B), although no significant differences were observed among the treatments (Table S1). Nonetheless, the relative abundance of Actinobacteriota decreased, while Pseudomonadota increased from 2019 to 2021 (Table S1). In 2019, Acidobacteriota showed a significantly higher relative abundance in DIV1 and MC than in DIV2. This difference disappeared by 2021, with no significant differences among the treatments (Table S1). Bacteroidota and Bacillota were significantly higher in DIV2 in 2019. In 2021, the phyla Bacillota was not identified, and Bacteroidota had the highest ($p < 0.01$) relative abundance in MC. Gemmatimonadota showed no significant differences across treatments on any of the sampling dates. Chloroflexota, however, had a significantly higher relative abundance in DIV1 than in the other treatments, but only in 2019. In 2019 and 2021, Planctomycetota showed the highest significant abundance in DIV1 and MC. Verrucomicrobia showed very low relative abundances in 2019 but increased their relative abundance $> 1\%$ in 2021, with no significant differences among the treatments (Table S1).

The bacterial genera were greatly affected by sampling dates and treatments (Figure 3C,D and Table S2). In 2019, the most abundant genera were *Streptomyces* and *Nocardioides* (in DIV1 and DIV2). *Bacillus*, *Nocardioopsis*, *Pelagibius* and *Woeseia* were significantly higher in DIV2. *Iamia*, *Mesorhizobium*, *MND1*, *Skermanella*, *Solirubrobacter* and *Sphingomonas* showed significantly higher relative abundances in DIV1 and MC. However, in 2021, *Haliangium*, *Microbacterium*, *Pseudonocardia*, *Solirubrobacter* and *Sphingomonas* showed significantly higher relative abundances in DIV1 and DIV2. The genus *Novosphingobium* showed a higher relative abundance only in DIV2, while *MND1* only showed a higher relative abundance in DIV1 (Figure 3C,D and Table S2).

FIGURE 2 | Principal Coordinate Analysis (PCoA) of bacterial communities at both sampling dates, 2019 (A) and 2021 (B). DIV1, mandarin diversified with barley/vetch and fava bean; DIV2, mandarin diversified with fava bean, purslane and cowpea; MC, monocrop with bare alley soil.

3.3 | Effects of Alley Cropping on Soil Borne Pathogens

Two of the seven soil borne pathogens measured were detected at both sampling times (2019 and 2021) (Table 1). The abundance of *Alternaria sp.* at both sampling times was higher than for *Colletotrichum sp.* Only, *Alternaria sp.* showed for DIV1 significant lower abundance than DIV2 and MC in 2021 (Table 1).

3.4 | Effect of Alley Cropping on Potential Functional Gene Abundance Related to C and N Cycling

Six genes that encode C degradation-related enzymes were analyzed. They were classified according to their metabolized compound types, including starch (*AMY*), hemicellulose (*abfA*, *manB*), cellulose (*cdh*, *naglu*) and chitin (*chiA*) (Figure 4A). In 2019, all the genes showed higher abundances in DIV1 than in MC (positive scores), while DIV2 showed lower abundances of these genes than MC (negative scores). This behaviour changed in 2021, when only *manB* showed a higher abundance in DIV2 than in MC (Figure 4A).

Ten genes related to N cycling encoding N fixation (*nifH*), nitrification (*amoA*, *hao*) and denitrification (*nosZ*, *nirS*, *narG*, *norB*, *norW*, *nrfA*) were analyzed (Figure 4B). DIV1 had a higher abundance of *nifH* than MC in 2019, while in 2021, both treatments (DIV1 and DIV2) showed higher abundances than MC (Figure 4B). The genes involved in nitrification (*amoA* and *hao*) showed lower abundances in DIV1 and DIV2 than in MC in 2019. However, in 2021, the potential abundances of both genes increased in DIV1 and DIV2 compared to MC. In general, the genes related to the denitrification process (*narG*, *norB*, *norW*, *nirB*, *nrfA*) showed higher abundances in DIV1 than MC in 2019 and lower abundances in DIV2, except for *nosZ*. In 2021, the behaviour of DIV1 and DIV2 was similar to 2019, with *narG*, *nrfA* and *nosZ* slightly increasing their abundances compared to MC (Figure 4B).

3.5 | Effect of Alley Cropping on Enzyme Activities

In 2019, the DH and the GlcNac showed higher activities in DIV2 than in the MC, while only DH increased in DIV1 compared to MC. The other enzyme activities showed lower values in DIV1 and DIV2 than in MC (Figure 5A). In 2021, all enzyme activities showed lower values in DIV1 and DIV2 than in MC (Figure 5A).

3.6 | Effect of Physicochemical Soil Properties on the Bacterial Community

The RDA carried out on the bacterial and physicochemical data showed that the first two axes explained 88.9% of the total variation (Figure 5B). Axis 1, which explained 66.7% of the total variation, separated DIV1 and DIV2 (positive scores) from MC (negative scores). Axis 2, which explained 22.2% of the total variation, separated DIV1 (positive scores) from DIV2 (negative scores). TOC, POC, TN and SWW were related to the bacterial community of DIV1, while EC, CEC, Mg and clay content were related to the bacterial community in MC (Figure 5B).

4 | Discussion

According to Sánchez-Navarro et al. (2023), the 3 years of alley cropping in the mandarin orchard increased land productivity and achieved several crops. The higher contents of organic carbon, soil TN and soil water content after 3 years driven the changed of soil bacterial community in DIV1. This association was probably due to the highest diversity of the aboveground vegetation by rotating three different crops, with enhanced root activity among the alley species (Ottaviani et al. 2019), as well as incorporating crop residues that may have increased soil organic matter and soil fertility (Zheng et al. 2018).

In 2019, both diversifications (DIV1 and DIV2) showed higher microbial activity due to the crops in the alley compared to bare soil in MC. However, the potential microbial activity related to C, N and P cycles, except for GLcNac activity, indicated that there were enough nutrients in the soil for plant and micro-organism growth, so there was no need to increase the

FIGURE 3 | Relative abundance of bacterial phyla and genera (> 1%) for both sampling times, 2019 (A and C) and 2021 (B and D). DIV1, mandarin diversified with barley/vetch and fava bean; DIV2, mandarin diversified with fava bean, purslane and cowpea; MC, monocrop with bare alley soil.

TABLE 1 | Abundance of pathogens for both sampling times.

(Log copy number g ⁻¹ soil)	DIV1	DIV2	MC
T1			
<i>Alternaria sp.</i>	6.55 ± 0.33	6.69 ± 0.49	6.45 ± 0.37
<i>Colletotrichum sp.</i>	3.94 ± 0.45	3.74 ± 0.26	4.07 ± 0.68
<i>Phytophthora sp.</i>	ND	ND	ND
<i>Xanthomonas fragariae</i>	ND	ND	ND
<i>Botrytis cinerea</i>	ND	ND	ND
<i>Xylella fastidiosa</i>	ND	ND	ND
<i>Xanthomonas campestris pv. campestris</i>	ND	ND	ND
T3			
<i>Alternaria sp.</i>	5.77 ± 0.20 ^a	6.63 ± 0.20 ^b	6.70 ± 0.22 ^b
<i>Colletotrichum sp.</i>	3.57 ± 0.40	4.00 ± 0.42	4.12 ± 0.27
<i>Phytophthora sp.</i>	ND	ND	ND
<i>Xanthomonas fragariae</i>	ND	ND	ND
<i>Botrytis cinerea</i>	ND	ND	ND
<i>Xylella fastidiosa</i>	ND	ND	ND
<i>Xanthomonas campestris pv. campestris</i>	ND	ND	ND

Note: 2019; T1 and 2021; T3. Letters after value mean significant differences ($p < 0.05$) for this parameter.

Abbreviations: DIV1, mandarin diversified with barley/vetch and fava bean; DIV2, mandarin diversified with fava bean, purslane and cowpea; MC, monocrop with bare alley soil.

FIGURE 4 | Log₂ fold-change (LFC) abundance of potential soil microbial functional genes related to C-degradation (A) and N cycling (B) at both sampling times (2019; T1) and (2021; T3). DIV1, mandarin diversified with barley/vetch and fava bean; DIV2, mandarin diversified with fava bean, purslane and cowpea; MC, monocrop with bare alley soil.

enzymatic machine. This is in agreement with Curtright and Tiemann (2021), who observed that the effect of management on enzyme activities depends on the enzyme category, the crops and the experimental and environmental factors.

Alley cropping changed the makeup of the soil bacterial community probably due to the relationships among the soil microbes and the rhizosphere of crops involved in the alley cropping sequence over the 3 years. Legume crops such as fava beans/cowpeas are among the most powerful nitrogen fixers through the nitrogen-fixing bacteria of their root nodes (Zhong et al. 2023). Sánchez-Navarro et al. (2023) showed that the fava beans in DIV1 showed no nodules in 2019 but they developed during the last crop cycle (2021), likely due to a stimulation of the soil rhizobia that established associations, which were not sufficiently abundant in 2019 to colonize the roots. The identification of Pseudomonadota in all the treatments could indicate the presence of nitrogen-fixing bacteria, increasing the efficiency of soil nitrogen use (Eilers et al. 2012). However, the

only genus observed in DIV1 in 2019 was a N fixers (*Mesorhizobium*). Besides symbiotic bacteria, there are also free-living bacteria able to fix atmospheric N, such as some species of the genera *Bacillus* and *Skermanella*, detected mostly in DIV2 in 2019 and in MC in 2021, respectively (Ladha et al. 2022). Besides, nitrogen-fixer bacteria could appear in the soils in an abundance < 1% although the analysis did not show it. Some authors have noted that the content of Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ in soil has been frequently increased nitrogen fixer populations in different agroecosystems (Wakelin et al. 2010), and we observed an association between the increase of Ca content and the bacterial community after 3 years, associated with the bacterial composition of DIV1.

In 2019, both diversifications (DIV1 and DIV2) showed lower presence of genes associated to nitrification process (*amoA* and *hao*) (Wankel et al. 2011). Genera such as *NMD1* and *Woeseia*, which significantly contribute to ammonia oxidation (Xiao et al. 2019) were detected in the diversification treatments. This

FIGURE 5 | Log₂ fold-change (LFC) of enzymatic activities for both sampling times (2019; T1 and 2021; T3) (A). Redundancy analysis (RDA) of the soil bacterial community and of soil physicochemical properties at the last sampling time (2021; T3) (B). GlcNac, β -1,4-*N*-acetylglucosaminidase; POC, particulate organic C; TOC, total organic C; CEC, cation exchange capacity; TN, total N content; Caex, exchangeable Ca; CL, clay content; SI, silt content; EC, electrical conductivity; SWFC, soil water content at field capacity 1500 kPa; Mgex, exchangeable Mg; BD, bulk density; SWW, soil water content; SA, sand content; DIV1, mandarin diversified with barley/vetch and fava bean; DIV2, mandarin diversified with fava bean, purslane and cowpea; MC, monocrop with bare alley soil.

could indicate less loss by lixiviation and a greater availability of nitrates to increase plant productivity and growth (Ayiti and Babalola 2022). However, after 3 years, both genes increased in both alley-cropping strategies with the presence of *NMD1*. This could indicate decreased plant available nitrogen. The majority are chemolitho-autotrophic aerobic bacteria that can use ammonium as their sole energy source and CO₂ as a carbon source (Kowalchuk and Stephen 2001). However, further investigation is necessary to clarify the other bacteria involved in this process.

Denitrification is the primary biological process responsible for returning fixed nitrogen to the atmosphere, thus completing the nitrogen cycle. This reduction of nitrate to nitrogen gas is

detrimental to agriculture, as it can deplete the soil of an essential plant nutrient, and losses can be considerable (Butterbach-Bahl and Dannenmann 2011). On the other hand, the excessive use of nitrogen fertilizers in agriculture has led to the accumulation of nitrates in groundwater and surface water, and denitrification is useful for removing nitrogen from these contaminated sources (Philippot and Hallin 2006). In our experiment, denitrification was higher in DIV1 than in MC in the first year and in both alley cropping systems after 3 years, pointing to a possible lack of nitrate contamination. The existence of nitrite reductase (NIR) and nitric oxide reductase (NOR) potential enzymes in non-denitrifying organisms indicates a broad physiological spectrum of these enzymes, not only for anaerobic metabolism but also for cellular detoxification

(Ye and Thomas 2001). Some species of genera *Pseudomonas*, only observed in higher abundance in DIV1 in 2019, are involved in the final step of denitrification related to *nosZ* gen (conversion of N_2O to N_2) (Krause et al. 2017). Gen *nosZ* increased on both sampling dates in the alley cropping systems, indicating the potential decrease of the greenhouse effect. Nonetheless, moments with greater activity ('hot moments') and points close to each other with greater denitrifying activity ('hot spots') make it difficult to accurately evaluate denitrification, especially considering that the studies have been carried out by taking samples at specific times (Vidon et al. 2010). Zhang et al. (2020) and Zhong et al. (2021) considered that nitrogen emissions are known to be higher in paddy fields than in drylands, which means that soil water content is a key factor affecting denitrification. This may be aligned with our results since DIV1 showed higher soil water content (SWW) than DIV2. Reduced oxygen and air space availability in soils, together with the decomposition of crop residues in the surface layers of the soil, are likely to favour anaerobic processes such as denitrification.

The different environmental conditions, crop types and diversity of compounds (i.e., glucose, cellulose and proteins) in the soil (Curtright and Tiemann 2021) affect the potential abundance of genes for soil carbon degradation (Huang et al. 2024). These genes increased in DIV1 in 2019, while in 2021, only genes related to cellulose and chitin remained high, regardless of the alley cropping system. Microbial communities balance their elemental requirements through selective degradation under different external conditions (Hu et al. 2022). Promoting potential carbon degradation gene abundance under alley cropping conditions could be an important ecological mechanism for maintaining microorganisms' elemental homeostasis in the soil (Luo et al. 2019). This aligns with authors such as Fernandez-Bayo et al. (2020), who have shown that organic exudates from the rhizosphere can increase C-degrading pathways.

The extent to which alley cropping can recruit beneficial soil bacteria that promote plant growth or show biocontrol activity is intriguing. Some species of *Bacillus*, *Streptomyces*, *No-cardioides*, *Solirubrobacter*, *Pseudomonas*, *Microbacterium*, *Novosphingobium* and *Pseudonocardia* genera associated to plant growth (Gonçalves et al. 2023) were observed in all the treatments, but with higher abundances in DIV1. There were also species of bacterial genera related to disease suppression, such as *Haliangium*, *Streptomyces* and *Pseudomonas* (Poveda et al. 2021; Cuartero et al. 2021). Also, the interaction of different microorganisms could also give rise, in many cases, to synergistic interactions that favour plant growth and/or suppress plant pathogen activity (Liu et al. 2024).

Among the well-known citrus microbial diseases, Alternaria brown spot (ABS), caused by *Alternaria* spp., and Anthracnose, caused by *Colletotrichum* spp., are two of the most important foliar fungal diseases (Timmer et al. 2000) detected in all treatments and only *Alternaria* sp. in 2021 in DIV1 diminished compared to the other treatments. Strains of genera of *Streptomyces*, (e.g., *Streptomyces odonnellii*) (Zhang et al. 2023), *Pseudomonas* and *Bacillus* showed a strong antifungal activity against citrus bacterial disease (Poveda et al. 2021).

5 | Conclusions

The findings of this study highlight the importance of alley cropping in maintaining soil functionality, increasing the potential abundance of genes related to carbon and nitrogen cycles and the abundance of plant growth-promoting bacteria. Here, we identified different genera of bacteria that have different species denominated beneficial microorganisms related to plant growth (i.e., *Bacillus* and *Pseudomonas*) and suppressive activity (i.e., *Haliangium* and *Streptomyces*), which were observed in both alley cropping systems in higher abundance than under monoculture. Most significant changes were observed in the diversification of the alley with a sequence of different crops every year (DIV1), rather than repeating the same crops (DIV2). This is likely due to the stimulation of beneficial bacteria through greater plant diversity, also related to a higher content of soil organic matter. Thus, orchard diversification with alley crop rotations should be fostered and encouraged as a sustainable practice to enhance soil and biodiversity conservation.

Author Contributions

Margarita Ros: funding acquisition, conceptualization, writing – original draft, writing – review and editing, validation, supervision. **Jessica Cuartero:** writing – review and editing, data curation, formal analysis, methodology. **Onurcan Özbolat:** data curation, formal analysis. **Virginia Sánchez-Navarro:** data curation, formal analysis, methodology, review and editing. **Marcos Egea-Cortines:** formal analysis, methodology. **Maria Almagro:** data curation, formal analysis, methodology. **María Hurtado-Navarro:** formal analysis, methodology. **Maria Martínez-Mena:** conceptualization, formal analysis. **Jose Antonio Pascual:** funding acquisition, conceptualization, review and editing, validation. **Raúl Zornoza:** funding acquisition, conceptualization, writing – original draft, writing – review and editing, validation.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in Zenodo at <https://zenodo.org/communities/diverfarming/>. Data are uploaded in <https://zenodo.org/communities/diverfarming/>.

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section.